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**First Language Interference in the Learning Process of
English as a Foreign Language in Young Learners.**

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Abstract:

This bibliographical thesis had as a general mission to analyze the first language interference process when learning English as a Foreign Language in young learners, with the idea of knowing to recognize how language interference affects the learning process, and in this manner identify learning strategies to avoid it. Have carried out this investigation was totally fruitful and helpful due to the need of change and innovation in Costa Rica`s classrooms, which have had many students who unconsciously always translate and compare with their mother tongue while learning English as a Foreign language. This thesis was based on the theoretical foundations of authors like Selinker (1972), Dulay (1982), Ellis (1997), Derakhshan & Elham (2015), Deller & Rinvolucris (2002), Guillon (2004). In agreement with the use methodology, it was catalogued as descriptive and its approach falls in qualitative due to the core of the investigation seeks to find out what are the interference factors over the learning process to come up with powerful and successful strategies in order to make a better engagement between students and the language . According to the results, most of authors concluded that the learning process might be affected by several factors, such as the excessive use of Spanish; however, the implementation of several methodologies and strategies to teach and learn a foreign language can make the difference.

Resumen:

Esta tesis bibliográfica tuvo como misión general analizar el proceso de interferencia del primer idioma cuando jóvenes estudiantes aprenden inglés como Lengua Extranjera, esto con el propósito de saber reconocer como la interferencia del lenguaje afecta el proceso de aprendizaje y de esta manera identificar estrategias de aprendizaje para evitar la interferencia. Haber llevado a cabo esta investigación fue totalmente provechoso y de gran ayuda debido a la necesidad actual de un cambio e innovación en las aulas de Costa Rica, las cuales han tenido muchos estudiantes los cuales inconscientemente siempre han traducido y comparado con su lengua materna mientras aprender inglés como Lengua Extranjera. La tesis se basó en los fundamentos teóricos de autores como Selinker (1972), Dulay (1982), Ellis (1997), Derakhshan & Elham (2015), Deller & Rinvolucris (2002), Guillon (2004). De acuerdo con la metodología de uso, la tesis fue catalogada como descriptiva y su enfoque recae in cualitativo debido a que el núcleo de la investigación busca conocer cuáles son los factores de interferencia sobre el proceso de aprendizaje para idear estrategias poderosas y exitosas con el fin de lograr un mejor compromiso entre los estudiantes y el idioma. Según los resultados, la mayoría de los autores concluyeron que el proceso de aprendizaje podría verse afectado por varios factores, como el uso excesivo del español; sin embargo, la implementación de varias metodologías y estrategias para enseñar y aprender un idioma extranjero puede marcar la diferencia.

Chapter I

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

At the present time, learning a foreign language has become an arduous task for students. During years in Costa Rica's education system students have been studying English as a Foreign Language, but they do not achieve the results expected when they have to interact using the target language learned. In Costa Rica, learners study English for 12 years approximately and by the end of their studies they are not capable of speaking the language. Unfortunately, they have been trying to understand the Language by translating words and phrases from English to Spanish and vice versa; nevertheless, the outcomes of years of studying do not reflect the knowledge and production of the language.

In Costa Rica, the curricula states that English teachers have to use the target language that they are teaching all the time during classes; therefore, learners create a word bank and understand more through the years.

When English professors try to speak and use only English during the lesson, learners exhibit a feeling of rejection against the language. For that reason, many professors end up teaching in Spanish the English lesson, or translating to the students which most of the time do not provide good results.

1.2 Problem Statement

In the classrooms of many Costa Rican education centers, teachers have been translating to teach English as a foreign language. Consequently, learners have created a strong teacher-student barrier in terms of communication, up to the point of making them incapable of think and speak in English neatly. One of the causes of this barrier and the current rejection of younger English students goes directly related to

how the first language interfere in their learning process and how they do not get positive outcomes when it comes to production and interaction with the English as a Foreign Language.

1.3 Justification

Over time, many students have been making many mistakes, when learning English, without realizing that those mistakes are some interferences between their first language (L1) to the target language (L2). As a matter of fact, some teachers have seen this as a common mistake; however, others have seen it as a downside. The whole problem has to do with students who unconsciously always translate and compare with their mother tongue while learning English as a Foreign language. This thesis aims to find out how first language interference affects (positively or negatively) the learning process of English as a foreign language making it either slower and less efficient or faster and best acquired. Thanks to a deep and detailed analysis, the reader might comprehend in a better way when interference occurs, how suppress it, and how to make the teaching-learning process useful and fruitful.

1.4 Objectives

1.4.1 General

- ❖ To analyze the first language interference process when learning English as a Foreign Language.

1.4.2 Specific:

- ❖ To recognize how the first language interference affects the learning process of English as a Foreign Language.

- ❖ To investigate about the different suggestions authors have regarding the First Language interference when learning English as a Foreign Language.
- ❖ To identify learning strategies for avoiding first language interference in young learners.

1.5 Scopes and Limitations

1.5.1 Scopes

The main scope of this research is to be able to get to analyze the first language interference process when learning English as a Foreign Language. and first language interference have become in one of the points of study of researches of the world due to the effects it has shown on the pedagogical area. Multiple characteristics are mentioned in this document supported by authors that are looking for exposing the functioning of this feature of foreign language learners during the learning stage.

By analyzing different sources of information to create this document the knowledge acquired along the composition is worth to share. Examination of details such as examination and compilation of benefits when applying this approach has been very useful for the new era of education we have nowadays.

1.5.2 Limitations

The main limitation of this research was the lack of material to analyze the topic being discussed due to language interference for foreign language learners is not being research. And those works which are available are unknown for many educators therefore foreign language interference is still in development for many researches.

Besides, another limitation is the time provide for this research. The time provided helps to have a decent investigation, but the time is crucial in order to have a deeper examination of sources consulted.

Chapter II

Literature Review

2.1 Literature review

Young English learners, in spite of their distinct experiences and background, deal with obstacles and complications when learning English as a Foreign Language. Some of those difficulties have possible short term or long term solutions, whereas some others have been object of analysis through the time causing the interest and concern of many English teachers who work with the idea of getting better outcomes when it comes to teach English as a Foreign Language. Language Interference is one of those that has gotten an extensive research and it is still quite interesting to investigate. When speakers or writers apply knowledge from their native language to a second language, it is called Language Interference.

The data collection in this chapter is from secondary sources, the secondary sources cited are from internet and library searches. The documents consulted are research articles, theses, journals and case studies that provide vital information to this study.

2.2 Interference

According to Selinker (1972) interference is the term for a dynamic linguistic system that has been developed by any learner of a second language (L2) who has not become fully skillful yet but is trying to approximate to the target language: preserving some features and rules of their first language (L1), or over generalizing the target language rules and creating innovations.

Dulay et al (1982) define interference as the automatic transfer, due to habit, of the surface structure of the first language onto the surface of the target language. Lott (1983) defines interference as 'errors in the learner's use of the foreign language that can be traced back to the mother tongue. Ellis (1997: 51) refers to interference as 'transfer', which he says is 'the influence that the learner's L1 exerts over the acquisition of an L2'. He argues that transfer is governed by learners' perceptions about what is transferable and by their stage of development in L2 learning. In learning a target language, learners construct their own interim rules (Selinker, 1971, Seligar, 1988 and Ellis, 1997) with the use of their L1 knowledge, but only when they believe it will help them in the learning task or when they have become sufficiently proficient in the L2 for transfer to be possible. Ellis (1997) raises the need to

distinguish between errors and mistakes and makes an important distinction between the two. He says that errors reflect gaps in the learner's knowledge; they occur because the learner does not know what is correct. Mistakes reflect occasional lapses in performance; they occur because, in a particular instance, the learner is unable to perform what he or she knows.

The truth is that there are many different opinions and thoughts about the huge world of interference when learning a foreign language, in order to enrich knowledge and learn even more, everyone should know how this world works and what are the different ways and views of interpreting the interference in the process of learning a language.

Scholars from different traditions have taken opposing views on the importance of this phenomenon. Chomsky (1986) typically regard variability in production as nothing more than common "performance errors", and not worthy of systematic inquiry or research, being seen as an inherent feature of the learners' production, where their preference for one linguistic variant over another depends on social variables such as the status or role of the interlocutor, phonological environment and the formality of the situation.

The most important psychological factor is usually taken to be attention to form and grammar, which is related to planning time. The more time that learners have to plan their activities, the more target-like their production may be. Thus, literate learners may produce much more target-like forms in a writing task having enough time to plan it, than in conversations where they must produce language with almost no planning time at all.

Affective factors also play an important role in the systematic variations of the interference. For example, learners in a stressful situation, such as a formal test, may produce fewer target-like forms than they would produce in a comfortable and casual setting. This clearly interacts with social factors related to the learner, attitudes and feelings toward the interlocutor and thoughts about the topic in discussion.

Specifically talking about learners, English produced by them often sounds and looks undeniably foreign compare with the native speakers' production. If the

mother tongue plays such an important role in the English produced by learners, it is clear that there will be a lot of varieties of English Learners. There are researchers in Second Language Acquisition (Nicholls, 2002) that given a piece of writing by a foreign learner of English, affirm that they can identify the mother tongue of the learner who wrote it. Learners use a wide number of strategies when they speak or write in the second Language. These include avoiding constructions or words they are unsure of, they tend to over use those they are confident about and take rules of English they have learnt and apply them in areas where they do not actually apply. In addition, the process of interference influences spelling, grammar and vocabulary decisions. When learners are not even thinking, they will simply translate complete phrases from their mother tongue or take individual words and transform them, where they need them, to make them look or sound English to overcome fissures in their vocabulary.

2.3 Foreign language acquisition

The only way that the acquisition of a second language starts to communicate in a second language is the time a learner begins to assume word-for-word translation equivalence or it is thought that every first language word has one translation in the second language by the learners, therefore, if learners of second language want to write or speak in the target language, they tend to rely on their first language structures. If the structures are different, then a lot of errors occur in the foreign/learning/target language thus this indicates an interference of first language on second language which creates misunderstanding during communication among speakers. Interference is the errors that can be traced back to the first language, while the learners use the second language. A learner has difficulties in second language such as phonology, vocabulary and grammar due to the interference of habits from first language (from now L1) and Second language (from now on L2. In fact, those errors that occur in learning of second language cause interference which are divided in three categories: the first category, developmental errors which are the errors that are not related to learner's first language. The second category, ambiguous errors which are the errors that involve interference and developmental errors. And the third category consists in unique errors which are those errors which cannot be categorized neither in interference nor

developmental errors. Interference is the result of old habits of the first language, for that reason those aspects must be eradicated to avoid having problems in the learning process. (Derakhshan & Elham 2015).

Learners of second language tend to transfer the forms, meaning and culture of their L1 to the foreign language and culture when attempting to speak the language. By learning L2 habits, L1 habits are also transferred and then the errors occur. Unfortunately, very few speakers achieve the goal of becoming fully bilingual, the learning process turns overwhelming for many speakers when they find out the abysmal differences from their first language compared to the second language which is being learned. Learners tend to block themselves when they realize there are some aspects that do not make sense from one language to the other, while other learners find fascinating these changes. Besides, there are two types of transfer in learning a second language: positive and negative transfer. In positive transfer, L1 facilitates the acquisition of second language, but in negative transfer the first language has negative impacts on L2 and interferes in L1. Indeed, when negative transfer occurs, we can study learners with different native language and compare them to find out the effect of L1 in learning a second language. First language can be considered as a tool for language acquisition to solve learning and communication problems. Also, communication must be seen as a skill that humans develop through the years, same case with the learning of a second language which is the interaction between mental and communicative process through which L2 learners develop their inter language skills by activating and using their previous linguistic knowledge acquired in the first language. Language can be highly influenced by the use of words from language to another, this not only interferes with the second language, it interferes with the first language as well. For that reason, speakers learning a second language can find themselves performing unconsciously the following characteristics: First, they can preserve their L1, but they cannot achieving native like L2 pronunciation. Second, they lose their L1 and achieve native-like L2 pronunciation. Third, they lose native-like pronunciation both in L1 and L2. (Derakhshan & Elham 2015).

One might suggest that having the use of two languages can create a sense of better understanding of the language where the communication skills and abilities

are improved. However, it occurs that learners are affected because of the impact and this leads to diverse consequences that are revealed when the production of the language is happening.

Learning a second language of Child vs. Adult is affected by the relationship between the age and some aspects of the second language. It is crucial for a language to be learned that the first interaction occur in the first stages of life which are during childhood. The childhood factor in building a second language can mark a difference along the process and success of the speaker. Moreover, the language must be learned before puberty, this stage means a whole change in the human capacity of learning a second language because the brain loses its elasticity and organizational capacities which are necessary for language acquisition. At an early stage, in childhood, human can learn languages, if it is not done, it will reduce by the stage of puberty. In childhood the left hemisphere is more involved in language and speech than right hemisphere. After that in stage of puberty, the two hemispheres become quite specialized for function because the children have inability in transferring and recalling the vocabulary of the first language. This is the advantage for them in learning a language without interference from their first language. Acquisition of second language before the age of about L2 has higher chance because lateralization is not completed yet. Children have more flexible brain than adults, thus the children are superior to adults in learning a second language. (Derakhshan & Elham 2015).

In a certain way, we can see children as playdough, they are moldable and elastic, that is why; for them is very easy to learn new words and a language itself because they are not afraid of making mistakes, even if they make, their parents normally do not correct them, the opposite in classrooms where teachers are very careful to grammar and phonology in second language learners.

First language transfers some parts of writing to second language when the speakers there are blanks of meaning or syntax in the message which cannot provide a clear meaning to people. When the speakers think that there is a lack of understanding many problems arise, because instead of obtaining a benefit of the first language it only creates more difficulties to comprehend the sentences. Language learners may use the L1 strategies in their L2 writing because of

similarities in L1 and L2. If the learner's knowledge of the target language is not enough, the learner relies on her or his L1 to express his or her idea and this reliance can be positive and negative. (Karim & Nassaji, 2013).

Learners of a second language before writing a document in the second language they first organize their ideas and thoughts using their first language. Once, they understand what their task is going to be about, learners proceed to create what it is being asked in the second language. This is a basic procedure but it helps speakers to find connection between ideas and paper.

2.4 Phonological Awareness

It has been proven that Phonological Awareness (PA) helps students to improve their speaking skills in the target language, they learn how to get along with others, not only partners but teachers too and to use with confidence new vocabulary and expressions in oral situations.

Phonological Awareness (from now on PA) is a hearing skill that is developed through a variety of activities and exercises that help teachers to expose students to the sound structure of the target language and teach them to identify, recognize and manipulate the sounds (Gillon, 2004). Activities proposed for PA are based on listening skills and must be developed first, before the speaking skills. This means that instruction and exercises should begin with tutoring of the teachers based on how to attend and distinguish different sounds like the environmental sounds and the sounds of speech. The early PA instruction involves the use of songs, rhymes and games to help students to become alert to speech sounds and rhythms instead of meanings. This strategy can be also used with young learners in general, because exposure to sound patterns in songs and rhymes are a start towards developing phonological awareness, however they should focus not only in the vocabulary but attending to the way the words sound. Therefore, different strategies and exercises must be implemented to aid students in becoming alert to noises instead. Some activities that involve students in attending to and demonstrating recognition of the new sounds of the foreign language include clapping hands when syllables are heard, stomping feet along with rhymes, talking like a robot for isolating sounds,

association of sounds with pictures. Basically, students do not need to know the alphabet for learning speaking properly.

PA skills can be developed in a predictable manner: from the largest units to the smallest units of sound. This means from words to syllables, from letters to phonemes. It should be noted that the acquisition of PA skills does not depend on a linear sequence; rather, learners continue to improve skills they have previously acquired while they learn new skills. Phonological awareness is an important determiner of success in learning to read and spell. For most learners, strong readers have strong phonological awareness, and poor readers have poor phonological awareness skills. Phonological awareness skills in the preschool and kindergarten years also strongly predict how well a child will read in the school years. In addition, interventions to improve phonological awareness abilities lead to significantly improved reading abilities. Phonological awareness instruction improves reading and spelling skills, but the reverse is also true: literacy instruction improves phonological awareness skills.

The relationship between phonological awareness and reading abilities changes over time. All levels of phonological awareness ability (syllable, onset-rhyme, and phoneme) contribute to reading abilities in the Kindergarten through second grade. However, beyond the second grade, phoneme level abilities play a stronger role. Phonological awareness and literacy is often explained by decoding (reading), when we are able to relate the writing of a word with its oral representation. This means that we identify the letters in words and match them to their sounds, and then combining the sounds to form a spoken word. On the other hand, encoding (spelling) is similar, however it goes in the opposite path, as we are able to identify the oral word and write it. It implicates determining the sounds in a verbal word, and then aligning those sounds into the letter sequence for spelling the written word. In both processes, encoding and decoding, phonological awareness is mandatory needed because the learner must know the different sounds in the words in order to relate them to the letter sounds. In most languages, like English, the written of the words do not correspond to the pronunciation and symbolic presentation is required. Every language has a different phonetic alphabet and a different set of possible phonemes and their combinations. The number of phonetic

symbols is between 20 and 60 in each language (O' Saughnessy, 1987). A set of phonemes can be defined as the minimum number of symbols needed to describe every possible word in a language. In English there are about 40 phonemes (Breen et al. 1996, Donovan 1996). Due to complexity and different kind of definitions, the number of phonemes in English and most of the other languages cannot be defined exactly.

The Gillon Phonological Awareness Training Program (Gillon, 2004) was designed for a research intervention in New Zealand. The purpose was to identify different techniques that could help teachers to improve the phonological awareness processes. It investigated the phonological awareness training effects on the ability, speech production, and literacy development of 5- to 7- year-old New Zealand children with spoken language difficulties but with normal intellectual capability, English is their first language, had correct abilities for comprehend all types of instructions and abilities and show no emotional disorders (Gillon, 2004). The final project had been modified since it ended in order to have more actualized information about speech production goals and activities; however, it originally contained a handbook made by speech - language therapists, a training workshop and a video in order to demonstrate the activities.

When the learners feel gaps in their L2 syntactical structures for writing in L2, they use syntactical structures of their first language (Bhela, 1999). Where there are similarities between the structures of L1 and L2 because of lack of understanding of the learners in L1 an error occurs in L2 (Bhela, 1999). In L2 writing, transfer can be considered both as a learning device and as a strategy to solve communication problems (Karim & Nassaji, 2013). Language learners may use the L1 strategies in their L2 writing because of similarities in L1 and L2. If the learner's knowledge of the target language is not enough, the learner relies on her or his L1 to express his or her idea and this reliance can be positive and negative (Karim & Nassaji, 2013). Ringborn (1987) points out the learners use L1 as a tool both for composing and for sampling the composing and for simplifying the complexity of the L2 writing task.

2.5 Advantages and disadvantages

The use of the first language when learning English as a foreign language has not been investigated in depth when it comes to advantages and disadvantages in the communication process, in fact we can say that depending on the area studied and the goal of the course it can vary from one place to another. Using the mother tongue is by no means a theoretical approach to the use of the first language. On the contrary, it is specifically designed to offer practical ideas and become a helpful resource for the foreign language teacher. Deller & Rinvoluceri (2002) emphasizes the idea that the foreign language teacher should use the students' mother tongue only in certain situations, for example: comparing English grammar with the mother tongue's grammar can be very positive for some learners. Beginners will probably progress at a quicker pace if the use of the mother tongue is allowed in the classroom. Translation exercises may also be the perfect practice when there is a grammar point that is causing trouble to students using or not using the mother tongue in second or foreign language acquisition deals mainly with the teaching methodology. In classes where teachers use the first language are referred to as using the traditional method or the grammar translation method, whereas classes where teachers do not use the first language are referred to those that use the direct method as a teaching methodology.

2.6 Strategies

As any student knows, our first language heavily interferes with the process of learning the second language. This is how it works: our brains use habitual patterns we know from our first language to establish any new hypotheses of how the new language works. It is reflected in everything, from phonetics to grammar, to semantics. This interference can be both negative and positive, depending on how similar your first language is to the one you try to learn.

a. Learning to Pronounce Sounds in Isolation

Different languages pronounce similar sounds in a (sometimes fundamentally) different manner, and one of the reasons why even grammatically correct speech of a non-native speaker may sound unnatural is because he uses pronunciation habits of his mother tongue. One of the ways to establish correct pronunciation is to train

pronouncing sounds in isolation, as separate entities, thus eliminating interference from preceding and following sounds in speech.

b. Mute Period

One of the methods of establishing right pronunciation right off the bat involves the use of a mute period – i.e., a period during which students are exposed to huge amounts of auditory materials in the language they study without trying to repeat what they hear. When students are later asked to produce the sounds of the new language, they sound much closer to native pronunciation than those who spend the same time actively practicing.

c. Using Writing Samples

Even reasonably advanced learners of English will often unconsciously fall back to formal grammar and syntax patterns from their first language. What is worse, often these patterns are not formally wrong according to the rules of English – they just look and sound unnatural, immediately betraying the ESL nature of their author. As teachers usually do not go as far as to correct them, these patterns can establish themselves as habits and are extremely difficult to root out later on.

One way to avoid it is hiring professional ENL writers to prepare great essays on the same topics the student has to write about. By comparing how he and they express the same ideas, the student will be able to notice the difference and compare patterns and structure used by native speakers with those he applies himself.

d. Full Immersion

One of the ways to quickly decrease the influence of mother tongue is a full immersion into the linguistic and cultural environment of the target language. If it is not possible, students should be exposed to as much content in the target language as possible (books, movies, music, etc.). The important thing here is that it does not mean doing more language exercises or studying more textbooks – immersion presupposes interaction with the language in a natural environment, while textbooks

and other learning materials are by definition unnatural and are built to teach particular rules.

e. Bilingual Practice

There are many types of bilingual practices, but in general, they follow the same idea: building connections between two languages that are deeper than mechanical word-for-word translations of sentences from one into another. For example, translation of short passages between two languages can be turned into a creative exercise by encouraging students to be free in their wording to make the result sounds as natural as possible – because it is precisely what they are going to do later on, when they have to interact with other people using the new language.

Interference of mother tongue with learning a foreign language is an influence that cannot be discounted – but if handled correctly, it can be limited or even used beneficially.

2.7 How to reduce the negative impact of L2-transfer on pronunciation?

G. Conti (2015) suggests that there are teaching strategies based on sensory-motor research findings on bilingual speech aimed at reducing the impact of negative first language transfer on L2 target language speech.

Firstly, in order to avoid interference from a grapheme's L1 phonological encoding on first introducing a new word it would be preferable not to expose the learners to its written form – this would avoid automated representation of the native phonological representation in Working Memory. In other words, it is better to present it orally, first in association with an image and, after some listening practice, to show it in its written form.

Secondly, L2 learners should be exposed to as much listening as possible in the context of a mute period before engaging in oral activities. Realistically speaking, in a typical state school classroom setting the pre-communicative mute period cannot be that long; but the most important lesson to be learnt from Neufeld's (1979) research is that students should not be thrown into unstructured communicative practice straight away after presenting the target lexical items. The listening activities

the students should be engaged in during this mute period should not only include test-like listening comprehension activities in the traditional sense: e.g. question and answer or true or false which focus solely on meaning. They should also include bottom-up processing activities that focus students on pronunciation and intonation, which involve matching words to sounds, such as jigsaw listening, gap-fills with options to choose from or , at the basic level, circling a word or phrase from a choice of three or four options.

Thirdly, the observation that students seem to perform challenging L2 phonemes (sounds) more effectively when pronounced in isolation would seem to suggest – according to Simmonds, Wise and Leech (2011) that a babbling phase in which students imitate the target speech sounds in isolation might also improve non-native pronunciation. This can be done at the beginning of a lesson as a warm-up activity – I have done it quite often and it can be fun, depending on how you pitch it to the student and how you conduct it. Or, it can be set a homework activity to be carried out at home for a few minutes, recorded and sent to the teacher for feedback (were the target sounds performed correctly? What could be done to improve them, etc.)

Finally, students need lots of practice in the context of structured and unstructured communicative activities. Such activities should, be staged after:

- Effective modelling of the correct pronunciation;
- The mute listening period discussed above;
- Extensive vocabulary practice through plenty of deep processing learning activities
- Structured oral activities (e.g. find someone who; structured surveys; role-plays with prompts; timed oral translations) preceded by sufficient preparation time
- (e) Less structured oral activities (at a later stage) in which students, through interviews, simulations, improvised role-plays, etc. converse freely about the topic-in-hand.

Traditional pronunciation drills (audiolingual style), minimal pairs and tongue-twisters or any other activities focusing students on pronunciation can be thrown in at

the pre-communicative stage, provided that they maintain students motivation high and the students understand and accept the rationale behind them.

In conclusion, it is up to teachers to decide – with the course requirement they teach on as well as the interest of the stakeholders in mind, of course – how much emphasis they should put on accuracy. What research shows is that plunging students into unstructured oral communicative practice straight away is not beneficial to the development of accurate pronunciation. The above strategies may not always be easy or practical to implement but are in my experience very effective in enhancing student grasp and execution of the target language pronunciation.

2.8 Reducing First Language Interference

a. Split Friendship Groups

You are more likely to have a gossip with your best friend than you are to be chatting away to someone you are not close to (or perhaps do not even like). One of the first things you can do to stop L1 interference is to split up people who are likely to chat together. Teenage girls are probably the biggest problem – they love talking with their friends, and the fact that they are sitting in a language class is not likely to put a stopper on it! Split up tight-knit friendship groups and the chatting will soon stop, especially if you mix the boys and girls together.

If you are worried about complaints from the students, try one of these methods to leave it a bit more to chance. You could pick their names out of a hat to dictate the seating order or have students pick playing cards or numbered slips of paper to see where they will sit.

b. Pick Your Battles

With low-level learners, or perhaps students that are particularly difficult to control, completely cutting out L1 can be a big task! If it seems impossible, try instead to have 'English only' activities or certain times of the class when students know there is a zero-tolerance policy on speaking L1. For example, in a free practice activity where students are going out on a limb and trying to be creative, it is probably much harder for them to control their L1 usage. However, during a

controlled practice (such as reading dialogues from a script in pairs) there is no excuse at all for speaking in their mother tongue. Make these activities L1 red flags, but be more lenient during freer practice.

c. Teach Useful Phrases

With low-level students, it may be fine for them to point at a flashcard and say 'Monkey! Banana!' but are they able to ask to go to the toilet in English? One of the most common reasons for L1 usage in the classroom, particularly with younger students, is simply that they just do not know how to say it in English. Teaching useful stock phrases like 'raise your hand', 'can I borrow a pencil' and 'please may I go to the toilet?' may seem like a waste of time with young learners – after all, a four-year-old won't necessarily know and understand every word in that sentence, even if they can say it beautifully. However, even if they don't understand it all, getting them to repeat these phrases will help to keep them in English, and will also give them a great prompt in the future for when they do come on to studying those grammatical structures.

d. No Easy Answers

Rather than allowing students to be overly reliant on dictionaries and translation tools (something particularly hard with Japanese students!) encourage your students to find other ways of finding out what they need to know. Rather than immediately trying to translate something, encourage them to explain what they mean using useful English phrases, such as '*it looks like a...*', '*you use it for...*', or '*you can buy it in...*'. In addition, encourage students to ask '*how do you spell...*' rather than immediately looking it up – if another student knows how to spell it, this will give them a chance to use their English too. Also, have a notebook handy so students can draw a picture to elicit what they mean. It's far more creative and keeps L1 out of the classroom.

Chapter III

Methodological Framework

3.1 Research Method

The Educational System in Costa Rica is dealing with an obstacle in terms of English-learning that most of students have suffered from and continue suffering, learning a foreign language has become a hard task and in spite of the majority of teachers are better due to their vocational and academic preparation, there is still a gap that impedes students succeed when trying to think and speak in English using it as a foreign language. If students did not translate (using their first Language) any time they want to express something, they would not make interference-mistakes and the results would be outstanding. Doing research and carrying out a bibliographic thesis Boon (2017) defines it as any research requiring information to be gathered from published materials. These materials may include more traditional resources such as books, magazines, journals, newspapers, and reports, but may also consist of electronic media such as audio and video recordings, and films, and online resources like websites, blogs, and bibliographic databases. In this interesting and deep topic related to the interference in the English learning process, the researcher will get the proper strategy, idea, way, technique, and help in order to accomplish the goal of making young students interact without making interference when learning a foreign language.

3.2 Type of Investigation

The type of research that is carried out is descriptive in order to analyze the first language interference in the learning process of English as a Foreign Language for young learners. A descriptive investigation, in its essence, descriptive studies are used to describe various aspects of the phenomenon. In its popular format, descriptive research is used to describe characteristics and/or behavior of the sample population, which in this case are the young students.

3.3 Research Approach

The research approach on this thesis falls in qualitative due to the core of the investigation which seeks to find out what are the interference factors over the learning process of English as a foreign language, besides, the suggestions brought by experts and the strategies to avoid or at least decrease this behavior on young speakers. According to Denzin and Lincoln (2005)

Qualitative research is a situated activity that locates the observer in the world. It consists of a set of interpretive, material practices that make the world visible. These practices transform the world. They turn the world into a series of representations, including field notes, interviews, conversations, photographs, recordings, and memos to self. This level, qualitative research involves an interpretive naturalistic approach to the world. This means that qualitative research study things in their natural settings, attempting to make a sense of, or interpret, phenomena in terms of their meanings people bring to them.

In other words, the qualitative research is not interested in numbers or statistics, it studied meticulously the behaviors and theories based on observation and field works that have an interpretation to the author, which is subjective. All the information sources are from different sites on internet which are reliable and accurate to what it is being studied in order to obtain the appropriate results for the analysis.

3.4 Population

The definition of population of a research can be explained as a comprehensive group of individuals, institutions, objects and so forth with have common characteristics that are the interest of a researcher. Therefore, the target population for this research are young students of seventh grade between the ages of 13 and 15 years old that attend classes in Liceo La Palmera, this public institution is located in the Province of Alajuela, it was founded in 2005 and has more than 300 students from 7th to 11th Grade. It has been proven that young students start the acquisition of the foreign language before the age of twelve; however, due to many deficiencies in the Costa Rican Educational System, many students get to seventh grade without learning enough English. As a matter of fact, young students have higher chances to avoid first language interference because lateralization is not completed yet, but when it comes to seventh graders that do not master the foreign language the task is harder. Of course children have more flexible brain than adults, however if the process of learning was not developed during the first stages (years) of learning the mother tongue, the language interference will affect their communication as well, that is why the topic is quite interesting to develop. So, the

target population mentioned above is clearly affected by these interferences which do not let students make progress and advance in their level of English. The idea is to find the proper strategy to help them avoid interference when speaking a Foreign Language.

3.5 Setting

The data will be collected by investigating different author's opinions and researches about First Language interference in the Learning process of English as a Foreign Language, once all the information is gathered, the researcher will identify one specific strategy or method that will become the best and more accurate and effective way of avoiding interference in young students of seventh grade.

Chapter IV

Results Analysis

4.1 Interference

According to Selinker 1972 interference is a system that is developed by the learner who is learning another language in he or she is not ready to communicate in the target language for that reason it affect the process of communication, Dulay in 1982 also defines interfering after the structure and a habit of the first language that affect the foreign language; moreover, we have Lott in 1983 that they point out that they interfering are errors in the Learners that use different language due to their mother tongue. However, Ellis a 1997 says that is transferable and it actually develops in the foreign language learner because Learners construct their own intern rules.

Nevertheless, Selinker said that the Learners will develop their knowledge in the second language if they do a learning task or that they feel sufficiently proficient to transfer words from the mother tongue to the foreign tongue. In the same way, Ellis stated that Learners must distinguish between errors and mistakes so they can reflect the gaps in their knowledge and improve their language use because now they know what is correct and incorrect.

On the other side, we have researchers like Chomsky which stated that the problems regarding to language is just another performance errors and they are really not worth it to do research about is just the future of the Learners production and it changes with the time and practice that's it

On the other hand, researchers like Nicholls in 2002 said that they can identify a piece of writing written by a foreign learner just by reading what they wrote because learners use the same strategies when they speak or write it in a foreign language; for instance, they tend to use the same structures in the repetition of specific words that are helping them.

4.2 Foreign language acquisition

In foreign language acquisition there are three categories which are the reason for the interference. Authors like Derakhshan and Elham (2015) stated that the first category, developmental errors which are the errors that are not related to learner's first language. The second category, ambiguous errors which are the errors

that involve interference and developmental errors. And the third category consists in unique errors which are those errors which cannot be categorized neither in interference nor developmental errors. Interference is the result of old habits of the first language, for that reason those aspects must be eradicated to avoid having problems in the learning process.

Moreover, Derakhshan and Elham (2015) also said that speakers learning a foreign language can find themselves performing unconsciously the following characteristics: First, they can preserve their L1, but they cannot achieving native like L2 pronunciation. Second, they lose their L1 and achieve native-like L2 pronunciation. Third, they lose native-like pronunciation both in L1 and L2.

On the other hand, Karim and Nassaji (2013) think that the First language transfers some parts of writing to foreign language when the speakers there are blanks of meaning or syntax in the message which cannot provide a clear meaning to people. When the speakers think that there is a lack of understanding many problems arise, because instead of obtaining a benefit of the first language it only creates more difficulties to comprehend the sentences. Language learners may use the L1 strategies in their L2 writing because of similarities in L1 and L2. If the learner's knowledge of the target language is not enough, the learner relies on her or his L1 to express his or her idea and this reliance can be positive and negative.

4.3 Phonological Awareness

According to Gillon 2004 is a hearing skill that is developed through a variety of activities and exercises that help teachers to expose students to the sound structure of the target language and teach them to identify, recognize and manipulate the sounds. He claims that activities proposed are based on listening skills and must be developed first, before the speaking skills. Moreover, this strategy involves the use of songs, rhymes and games to help students to become alert to speech sounds and rhythms instead of meanings.

As examples of some activities that involve students in attending to and demonstrating recognition of the new sounds of the foreign language include:

- Clapping hands when syllables are heard.

- Stomping feet along with rhymes.
- Talking like a robot for isolating sounds.
- Association of sounds with pictures.

Basically, Gillon stands out that students do not need to know the alphabet for learning speaking properly. In other words, Phonological Awareness skills can be developed in a predictable manner. This means from words to syllables, from letters to phonemes.

Phonological awareness is an important determiner of success in learning to read and spell. Gillion's research states that for most learners, strong readers have strong phonological awareness, and poor readers have poor phonological awareness skills. Phonological awareness skills strongly predict how well a child will read in the school years. In addition, interventions to improve phonological awareness abilities lead to significantly improved reading abilities. Phonological awareness instruction improves reading and spelling skills, but the reverse is also true: literacy instruction improves phonological awareness skills.

All levels of phonological awareness ability (syllable, onset-rhyme, and phoneme) contribute to reading abilities. Phonological awareness and literacy is often explained by decoding (reading), when we are able to relate the writing of a word with its oral representation.

To support Gillion's theory, O' Saughnessy in 1987 explains that Phonological awareness and literacy is often explained by decoding (reading), when we are able to relate the writing of a word with its oral representation. This means that we identify the letters in words and match them to their sounds, and then combining the sounds to form a spoken word. On the other hand, encoding (spelling) is similar, however it goes in the opposite path, as we are able to identify the oral word and write it. It implicates determining the sounds in a verbal word, and then aligning those sounds into the letter sequence for spelling the written word. In both processes, encoding and decoding, phonological awareness is mandatory needed because the learner must know the different sounds in the words in order to relate them to the letter sounds.

O' Saughnessy mentions that every language has a different phonetic alphabet and a different set of possible phonemes and their combinations. Therefore, he stayed with the fact that in most languages, like English, the written of the words do not correspond to the pronunciation and symbolic presentation is required.

Besides, Breen et al. 1996, and Donovan in 1996 add to this that a set of phonemes can be defined as the minimum number of symbols needed to describe every possible word in a language. In English there are about 40 phonemes, so due to complexity and different kinds of definitions, the number of phonemes in English and most of the other languages cannot be defined exactly.

Thanks to Gillon Phonological Awareness Training Program in 2004, he could be able to identify different techniques that could help teachers to improve the phonological awareness processes. It investigated the phonological awareness training effects on the ability, speech production, and literacy development of 5- to 7-year-old New Zealand children with spoken language difficulties but with normal intellectual capability.

Bhela in 1999 said that when the learners feel gaps in their L2 syntactical structures for writing in L2, they use syntactical structures of their first language, where there are similarities between the structures of L1 and L2 because of lack of understanding of the learners in L1 an error occurs in L2.

Karim & Nassaji in 2013 said that in L2 writing, transfer can be considered both as a learning device and as a strategy to solve communication problems. Plus, they mentioned that Language learners may use the L1 strategies in their L2 writing because of similarities in L1 and L2. If the learner's knowledge of the target language is not enough, the learner relies on her or his L1 to express his or her idea and this reliance can be positive and negative.

Ringborn in 1987 pointed out that the learners use L1 as a tool both for composing and for sampling the composing and for simplifying the complexity of the L2 writing task.

4.4 Advantages and Disadvantages

Deller & Rinvoluceri in 2002 emphasizes the idea that the foreign language teacher should use the students' mother tongue only in certain situations for example: comparing English grammar with the mother tongue's grammar can be very positive for some learners beginners will probably progress at a quicker pace if the use of the mother tongue is allowed in the classroom translation exercises may also be the perfect practice when there is a grammar point that is causing trouble to students using or not using the mother tongue in second or foreign language acquisition deals mainly with the teaching methodology. In classes where teachers use first language are referred to as using the traditional method or the grammar translation method, whereas classes where teachers do not use first language are referred to those that use the direct method as a teaching methodology.

4.5 How to reduce the negative impact of L2-transfer on pronunciation?

G. Conti in 2015 suggests that there are teaching strategies based on sensory-motor research findings on bilingual speech aimed at reducing the impact of negative first language transfer on L2 target language speech.

First of all, it is relevant and preferable not to expose the learners to the written form. In other words, it is better to present it orally, first in association with an image and, after some listening practice, to show it in the written form.

Second, L2 learners should be exposed to as much listening as possible in the context of a mute period before engaging in oral activities. Neufeld's in 1979 said that the most important lesson to be learnt is that students should not be thrown into unstructured communicative practice straight away after presenting the target lexical items. The listening activities the students should be engaged in during this mute period should not only include test-like listening comprehension activities in the traditional sense. They should also include bottom-up processing activities that focus students on pronunciation and intonation, which involve matching words to sounds, such as jigsaw listening, gap-fills with options to choose from or , at the basic level, circling a word or phrase from a choice of three or four options.

Third, the observation that students seem to perform challenging L2 phonemes (sounds) more effectively when pronounced in isolation would seem to suggest according to Simmonds, Wise and Leech in 2011 that a babbling phase in which students imitate the target speech sounds in isolation might also improve non-native pronunciation. This can be done at the beginning of a lesson as a warm-up activity.

Finally, students need lots of practice in the context of structured and unstructured communicative activities. Such activities should, be staged after:

- Effective modelling of the correct pronunciation;
- The mute listening period discussed above;
- Extensive vocabulary practice through plenty of deep processing learning activities
- Structured oral activities (e.g. find someone who; structured surveys; role-plays with prompts; timed oral translations) preceded by sufficient preparation time
- Less structured oral activities (at a later stage) in which students, through interviews, simulations, improvised role-plays, etc. converse freely about the topic-in-hand.

Based on G. Conti it is up to teachers to decide – with the course requirement they teach on as well as the interest of the stakeholders in mind, of course – how much emphasis they should put on accuracy. What he shows is that plunging students into unstructured oral communicative practice straight away is not beneficial to the development of accurate pronunciation. The above strategies may not always be easy or practical to implement but are in my experience very effective in enhancing student grasp and execution of the target language pronunciation.

Chapter V

Strategies

5.1 Strategies

The learning process has to be successful in order to make an engagement between students and the language. A good classroom environment always has some elements of creativity thanks to great strategies or activities that make the lessons more interesting and interactive. When activities and creativity are present in classrooms, students have more opportunities to learn, grow, explore and express themselves. Undoubtedly, the implementation of appropriate activities encourages students to learn new things. Besides, activities help improve students' emotional and social skills. Even when teachers teach tough lessons, activities make students learn with fun and ease. The following activities are focused on avoiding first language interference in young learners when learning English as a second language.

Table 1

Activity #1	Recommended by Guillon (2004) / Phonological Awareness
Name	Robot Repetition
Level	Seventh Grade
Unit:	Two
Scenario:	Enjoying life
Theme:	My Daily Routine
Objectives:	To recognize the sound of most words heard in context To Understand simple information and phrases about routines.
Materials:	Videos (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JwGnClSLOpU)

Activities:	The teacher shows a video about daily routines and tells students to pay attention to the sounds. After that, the Teacher plays the role of the inventor and stands on one side of the classroom. Students are the robots and line up alongside each other at the other end of the classroom waiting for their turn. The inventor chooses a student/robot and gives them a short sentence such as, "Every morning my mum cooks pancakes". If the student repeats it correctly, they take a step forward and wait for their next turn. If the student does not repeat the sentence correctly, they take a step back. As the robots move forward make the sentences longer and more complex (e.g. "On Sundays my siblings mow the lawn right after cleaning the backyard"). The winner is the first robot to reach the inventor.
Purpose :	Our brain must hear the words, make sense of them and then remember them long enough to complete the direction. It is an essential skill in the classroom as it is the foundation of following directions and instructions, writing to dictation and successful note taking.

Elaborated by the researchers

Table 2

Activity #2	Recommended by Guillon (2004) / Phonological Awareness
Name	Sound–Source Matching
Level	Seventh Grade
Unit:	Three
Scenario:	Getting Back to Nature
Theme:	Where can I go next?
Objectives:	To recognize specific information on natural beauties and wonders. To recognize some isolated vocabulary terms about nature.
Materials:	Sound clips of various animal noises (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VSGy007Awzq)- Picture cards of various animals (Annex # 1)

Activities:	In an imaginary scenario, the Teacher takes all students to the Zoo and asks them to match the sound of every animal to the animal pictures. The teacher spreads the animal picture cards out on the floor in front of the students and starts playing the clips. Then prompts each student to connect the animal sound clips to the pictures.
Purpose:	To help students learn about their sense of hearing, and teaching them to differentiate between various sounds.

Elaborated by the researchers

Table 3

Activity #3	Recommended by Guillon (2004) / Phonological Awareness
Name	Treasure hunt
Level	Seventh Grade
Unit:	Six
Scenario:	Getting from Here to There
Theme:	Knowing how to get there
Objectives:	To follow simple directions to get from one place to another
Materials:	Plastic maps (Annex # 2), and markers.
Activities:	The teacher gives every student a map of a city; he explains that they must search for a treasure by following a set of clues which will be said aloud. Students listen to the directions and find their way along the map to the secret location, all the streets are labeled and the buildings are marked. Once the teacher is done, he asks students where they ended up.

Purpose :	To practice and learn language skills while engaging in the problem solving represented by deciphering a series of clues that show the way to a “treasure” (generally a small, age-appropriate prize or reward).
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Elaborated by the researchers

Table 4

Activity #4	Recommended by Ellis (1997) Error recognition
Name	My shopping list
Level	Seventh Grade
Unit:	Four
Scenario:	Checking things off a shopping list
Theme:	Going Shopping
Objectives:	To recognize different mistakes from written sentences in students' exercises.
Materials:	Video shopping at the grocery store https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GINbzAGZC2M&ab_channel=EasyEnglish
Activities:	Teacher gives basic information about shopping preferences and prices. Learner describes shopping items using simple words and sentence frames. (for example, their size, color, material, price)
Purpose :	To write short, simple texts about shopping at grocery stores, clothing stores and supermarkets to check the difference between English and Spanish for describing places and products to find the errors made.

Elaborated by the researchers

Table 5

Activity #5	Recommended by G. Conti (2015) / Sensory-motor
Name	Holidays
Level	Seventh Grade
Unit:	Five
Scenario:	Let's Celebrate Costa Rican Culture!
Theme:	How Costa Ricans celebrate national "Tico" culture
Objectives :	To ask for specific information regarding holidays and celebrations. To compare celebration in Costa Rica and USA by interacting during the lesson.
Materials:	video holidays https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=v8CYKJK6AQI&ab_channel=RossmerySolanoSolano
Activities:	The teacher presents a comparison chart between celebrations in Costa Rica and United States. Students talk about celebrations and holidays in Costa Rica briefly. Students also bring typical items used for the celebrations and explain their use to the others.
Purpose :	Learners get to work in the sensorimotor by exploring and exposing items during the class for the topic of holidays.

Elaborated by the researchers

Table 6

Activity #6	Recommended by G. Conti (2015) / Accuracy
Name	Flash Cards
Level	Seventh Grade
Unit:	Six
Scenario :	Getting from Here to There
Theme:	Knowing what I need and when
Objectives:	To describe weekend or holiday plans with use of traveling vocabulary when booking, shopping or traveling.
Materials:	Traveling https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LzX4zrPRGts&ab_channel=TonyIllustratedEnglish
Activities :	The teacher provides the flashcard of different scenarios to travel. Students have to express preferences about places to visit and ways to move around. And also interact around with the flash cards, asking questions about places, where they are and how to get to them and answering such questions.
Purpose :	To enhance the communication and performance in different situation where pronunciation and accuracy is important to deliver and understand a message.

Elaborated by the researchers

Table 7

Activity #7	Recommended by Derakhshan and Elham (2015) / Interference
Name	False cognates
Level	Seventh Grade
Unit:	Two
Scenario:	Enjoying Life
Theme:	Hanging out
Objectives:	To describe how to enjoy life by using simple, standard expressions and false cognates.
Materials:	False cognates https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IbHn9h-j4bA&ab_channel=AlejoLoperIngl%C3%A9s
Activities:	The teacher asks the students what they do when they hang out. Students have a list of false cognates that they have to use correctly by doing a presentation describing situations in which they hang out.
Purpose :	To recognize the interference that can occur in communication due to errors like the use of false cognates.

Elaborated by the researchers

Table 8

Activity #8	Recommended by Guillon (2004) / Phonological Awareness
Name	Describe the Setting
Level	Seventh Grade
Unit:	Five
Scenario:	Let us Celebrate Costa Rican Culture!
Theme:	How my family and I celebrate "Tico" culture
Objectives:	<p>To recognize basic phrases that denote facts about Costa Rican culture.</p> <p>To understand pieces of short information about holidays and celebrations</p>
Materials:	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KxOwGzaBpmg
Activities:	The teacher shows a video related to Costa Rica`s Culture and tells students to pay close attention to the details. Then he asks students to describe the setting they liked the most and mention one tradition or food that caught their eye.
Purpose :	To train students to grasp specific information, details that are relevant, important or necessary. The goal is to help students obtain the detailed information they may need.

Elaborated by the researchers

Chapter VI

Conclusions

6.1 Conclusions

Teaching English can be very challenging. The learning process might be affected by several factors. One of those factors is the use of Spanish during the English classes due to the lack of knowledge of the foreign language, which do not help the learners to acquire a language. This interference in the process, as researches like Ellis and Lott have mentioned in this document, slows down the process and the student feels unable to develop good understanding and use of the language in a daily basis.

Teacher and learners have to explore the differences and similarities of both first and foreign language in order to establish a successful communication process. The previous studies showed that first language can have a negative or positive transfer on foreign languages. Where the structures of two languages are different, negative transfer occurs, and where the structures of two languages are similar, the positive transfer occurs and first language facilitate the foreign language learning. It was found that first language has interference in second language. A lot of factors that cause interference were considered such as the similarities and differences in the structures of two languages, background knowledge of the learner, proficiency of learners on second languages, and the structures.

In general, we can find several methodologies and strategies to teach and learn a foreign language even though we may have first language interferences. It all falls into the context and commitment of the speaker who aims to master it.

Chapter VII

Recommendations

6.2 Recommendations

Based on the conclusions made, there is still a need to further investigate on the other aspects of English language learning. The subjects of this study were High school students of seventh grade. Therefore, the result of this study may not be true to all students.

A short-term remedial course in speaking especially designed for proficient or non-proficient students be conducted or given to students during the time they are in high school to minimize the use of the first language. The remedial instruction should be given to first year students after finishing the first semester when they can see the performance of the student during the English classes. The area should focus on speaking and listening since this is where the students usually fall short, as an example of that the phonological awareness. To facilitate this, the researchers have proposed to expose the student to the foreign language, compare them and realize that there are similarities and differences that can impact positively or negatively the learning.

Foreign language learners, particularly those of lower proficiency usually lack the ability to express or verbalize their thoughts confidently, clearly and accurately. Thus, although the teachers should, of course, encourage strongly the use of English among students of low proficiency and even to students of high proficiency, the teachers should also expect that a certain level of dependence on the first language is necessary for the students for the students to carry out the procedure effectively and to gain from it. For all those reasons, as a way to encourage the students to use foreign language more, teachers can utilize strategies that provide students opportunity to practice their speaking and listening skills in the target language. This is because the students view the procedure as giving them the opportunity to improve their English rather than just obtaining good grades to pass the course.

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Annexes

I annex:

Il annex:

